

REFLECTION AND JUSTIFICATION

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The syllabus is based on notional-functional syllabus. According to Balconi (2021), it is essential that ESP courses need to include the form of language based on content. The lesson is conducted via cognitive functions depending on different language functions in order to acquire language unconsciously. Students need to learn English rather than learning in English (Dutro & Moran,2003).

Target learners are learned English according to IELTS assessment. The lesson is conducted focusing on all language skills but it is relevant to emphasize their context. IELST certification is for only document, together with this, they should acquire natural English and their context in detail because their fashion shows will be held on abroad. They should have enough knowledge to exchange ideas or to comprehend native speakers' speech. Every lesson is conducted based on two receptive or productive skills via appropriate context for designers. Daily assessment includes in mostly self-correction, feedback each other's work and also the role of teacher is not correcting learners' mistakes after answering or giving own opinion, they should acquire their mistakes during the lesson and at the end of the lesson the teacher should give positive feedback for their mistakes via recommending suitable ways.

The Lesson Plan includes in all essential components for the whole lesson from beginning to end. All information even about students or number of students, level, date, room is essential. Even if the teacher can't conduct lesson or has some problem, his or her colleagues can follow instructions and conduct the lesson easily and clearly. The teacher knows about how many materials or copied worksheets are enough or necessary for number of learners. They are aware of what they do during the lesson. I tried to adopt my target learners. Lesson objectives are written according to learners' needs. Content one is based on learners' context because of ESP, language objectives are related to language aspect such as, any grammar structure, key vocabularies (Ashcraft, 2014). Lesson plan procedures cover all things what both teachers and students do during the lesson, namely sequences of each stage, time for every activity. Even students

can be aware of objectives of lesson, have a chance to analyze the lesson with others. Procedure also includes classroom routine the teacher should choose according to learners' age (Vogt & Short, 2008). This can help students to follow instructions easily, know what they expect or do about attending in class. Assessment can be formative based on daily assignments, summative is revised one more time at the end of the lesson. Reflection occurs in the class or after it. According to Brown (1994), the teacher can't gain success or make adjustments for next class without evaluating the plan.

Moreover, scaffolding, differentiation were modified according to learners' needs. According to Farrel (2002), I added teaching aids which a number of technologies or methods the teacher uses during the lesson. Essential question is also relevant because learners know topic related questions in the lesson (Barrera et.al,2003). Group options can be different according to learners' number, gender, ages, same or different first language as a pair, small groups or individual work. Scaffolding includes in modeling, guided practice, independent practice and it can be verbal, procedural as well as instructional (Barrera et.al., 2003). These cover even teacher's position and clarify teacher's role in the lesson. Differentiation helps lower level students among higher ones by applying extra task in the lesson or at home (Greek, 2021). After PPP, students should do self-correction via giving feedback among learners according to producing activity same as creating post stage in

Bloom's Taxonomy.

Differentiation activities are conducted for beginner, elementary and preintermediate level learners. The level of students can be different in the same class.

Differentiating content can be proper for students' needs, level, interests.

Warm-up activity is conducted based on new theme to check learners' background knowledge. It improves learners' thinking skills effectively. According to

Tomlinson (2001), it is essential to provide printed even simple materials to take note rather just taking note. Because printed material includes some key words, students can be aware of why they watch video and what content the video includes in. that's why I modified taking note activity in last formative assessment taking note in printed materials that include key categorized words. This stage activity focuses on receiving topic-based vocabulary. Because learners are designers, they should learn clothing items in detail. That's why I

modified video for them. I downloaded four videos related to four seasons clothing separately and I made them as a full video by adding and editing.

While stage of differentiation activity is related to group options, firstly it is conducted in peers and then small groups via discussing, debating and self-correction.

Hadaway (2009) noted that the importance listening that includes content and concept based vocabulary, same style and flexible use of language to acquire their context without translation in first language and dictionary use. Matching activity based on listening comprehension improves learners' critical thinking and thinking aloud skills. Students have not enough thinking skills in target language. Moreover, differentiating process activity focuses on encouraging students to make sense of opinion via appropriate way, kinesthetically, critically, verbally according to learners' profile (Tomlinson, 2001). The listening activity focuses on learners' comprehension and improving their vocabulary by writing proper descriptions. This task was not copied and pasted from ready-made sources. Listening track, pictures and descriptions were taken and modified differently according to the level of learners. The last stage of activity that is original task is differentiating production that is making recommendations for our community. This is also based on our cultural and socio-cultural points. Students should give self recommendation as designers which means that they answer from totally designer's look. The content and language is associated with each other in this stage. In shortly, they produce via different instructions according to learners what they have learned so far. The important thing is focusing on vocabulary why, students do not know enough content-based vocabulary in their field. Assessment includes formative, summative, peer feedback. Formative one includes self-feedback among learners after that a teacher. It is revised one more time in summative assessment and checked by a teacher.

Scaffolding

All differentiated activities have been selected according to learners' needs.

They can learn language easily via the usage of their content, job that can be motivation for them. The usage of scaffolding is related to learning style. In this lesson, students work individually, in peers as well as small groups. Firstly, they learn topic based vocabulary while watching video. Then they do listening task according to their content and then they produce what they have received linked in background knowledge and cultural concepts for giving recommendation. They can share their ideas in this friendly, collaborative atmosphere via using

realia, posters, connecting to background knowledge. Finally, they assess themselves and give self feedback because students can comprehend easily their mistakes through groupmates feedback.

